

Engineering Students' Adaptation to the Online Education System and the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Learning

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The COVID pandemic accelerated digital learning in tertiary institutions. Engineering, as a practice-based profession, faced significant challenges in delivering comprehensive training in developing countries during the post-COVID era. This paper examines how engineering students have adopted online learning alongside the use of artificial intelligence for acquiring knowledge. Data were collected from engineering students at three tertiary institutions in two northwestern Nigerian states using an online survey. The survey was promoted through students' online groups over two weeks in February 2024. The data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics 23. Participants reported that most engineering courses are still taught in person, despite the availability of broadband facilities at the institutions. Many students are unfamiliar with a wide range of AI tools, apart from a few AI chatbots used for learning and assignments. The cost of broadband subscriptions and smartphones limits students' ability to access AI tools for learning. While most students are aware of AI tools that use Natural Language Processing, they rarely use them to their full potential. Many students cannot afford laptops and therefore rely on smartphones, which have limited capacity for supporting engineering education. When properly guided and monitored, digital learning tools incorporating AI can effectively supplement traditional engineering education methods for students' learning.

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Introduction

Global educational institutions have faced enormous challenges with the outbreak of COVID-19, as more than 1.5 billion children in 2/3 of the world's countries could not access educational facilities during the period of the epidemic. (Mamedova et al., 2023; Taryn, 2020). Engineering education, a professional field traditionally based on practical and tutorial teaching, was significantly affected. As a field that strives

to solve human and societal problems that require systematic analysis and simulations, it is itself faced with the need to adapt and adopt its method of transmission of knowledge (Shadnaz et al., 2020).

The development of Industry 4.0, which stems from engineering, has caused many other fields to evolve into e-learning and online formats learning. However, because of the practical nature of engineering education, adapting to such a mode of transmitting knowledge was not widely adopted in

Engineering (Abdulkareem et al., 2022). More affected are developing countries, which have fewer resources dedicated to educational teaching and research. Before the outbreak, Engineering Colleges and Universities in developed nations had developed models that experimented with e-learning and online learning. Many of these institutions that are less dependent on government have gone independent in policy and finances.

However, in developing nations, most colleges and universities rely heavily on the government and are usually affected by their country's economic challenges. In fact, 40% of countries worldwide, which are mainly developing or economically disadvantaged, were unable to provide educational support during the COVID-19 pandemic (Taryn, 2020). Additionally, the availability of funds for research in most developing countries primarily depends on the government, mainly due to the gap between academic institutions and industries. Despite the challenges stated and others, developing countries such as Nigeria cannot afford to lag further behind by not adopting e-learning and utilising artificial intelligence (AI) in their educational institutions. Such adaptations are a critical requirement for developing a knowledge-based society (Park, 2009). Moreover, adaptation of AI for learning has been linked to the future of tertiary education and is expected to continue to grow significantly (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). The fast rate of adopting Large Language Models such as ChatGPT attests to such a statement (Baek et al., 2024; Ravšelj et al., 2025). As observed in other countries, the COVID-19 outbreak experience should provide an opportunity for institutions to modify their teaching methods to safeguard against future challenges. This study is focused on investigating how

Engineering students in the northwestern part of Nigeria have adapted to e-learning and online learning practices for academic purposes. The findings from this study will help to educators and administrators to have a better understanding of the students' perception of online learning and AI. The availability of such information will help educators and administrators of institutions to know how students are likely to embrace e-learning and AI in learning. Hence, policymakers and administrators would be aware of the modalities that can be adopted to promote e-learning in tertiary institutions.

Methods

A convenience sampling cross-sectional study conducted online using Google Form was developed and sent to the social media groups made up of only Engineering students in one university each from Kebbi and Sokoto State and a Polytechnic from Kebbi in the Northwestern part of Nigeria. The students were informed of the intended participants and instructed not to forward to non-engineering groups.

The Procedure and Instrument

The questionnaire was adapted from previous studies on e-learning adoption, online learning experiences during COVID-19 and AI usage in higher education (Aristovnik et al., 2020; Park, 2009; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). The survey was opened to current students and those who graduated in the 2023/2024 Academic Session. After obtaining approval from the three institutions, the questionnaires were forwarded to the concerned students. The purpose of the data collection was explained to the students, and they were assured of the confidentiality of the information provided. The online survey consists of twenty-one

questions. The questions comprised demographic information such as department and year of study. Data about the availability of tools in the institution, such as computers, phones, internet facilities, modes of research and which one is preferred, types of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools and usage, etc. Four variables were used to measure the Engineering students' disposition to the use of AI for learning. The four variables were measured using a Likert scale. Most of the questions assessing participants' perceptions were measured using a 5-point Likert scale. The students' response was limited to two semesters in two academic sessions. The form was developed and vetted to ensure construct and content validity. Thereafter, the link to the Google form was forwarded to the social media group of the students from the three institutions running engineering programmes, with instructions to send only to Engineering students.

Statistical Analysis

The data were collected in csv format and exported into IBM SPSS Statistics 23. Descriptive statistics was used to investigate the frequency distribution of the demographic variables. Correlation techniques such as the T-test and ANOVA, χ^2 test, etc., were used to compare the students' responses. The Spearman Correlation technique was used to investigate the significant association among variables. For the test comparing means, a test for homogeneity of variance was conducted to ensure sufficient sampling of different responses. All analyses were performed at a significant level of $p < 0.05$.

Results

Demography

Table 1 presents a summary of the major responses by the participants.

Table 1: Summary of Participants' Responses

	Frequency	Percentage
Engineering Department		
Civil	19	12.2
Electrical	29	18.6
ICT	12	7.7
Mechanical	83	53.2
Others	13	8.3
Year in School		
UG1	2	1.3
UG2	18	11.5
ND	3	1.9
UG3	29	18.6
UG4	28	17.9
HND	25	16.0
UG5	29	18.6
Graduated	17	10.9
No response	5	2.2
Laptop		

Yes	76	48.7
No	75	48.1
No response	5	3.2
Smartphone		
Yes	149	95.5
No	0	
No response	7	4.5
Online or e-learning courses in last sessions		
1	54	34.6
2	34	21.8
3	12	7.7
4	9	5.8
5	6	3.8
6 to 9	12	7.7
10 to 15	14	9.0
More than 15	4	2.6
No response	11	7.1
Lecture mode Preference		
Physical classroom	52	33.3
Online Classroom	28	17.9
Mixed mode of Physical and online	73	46.8
No response	3	1.9
Preference for Lecture Materials		
Hard copy	16	10.3
Soft copy	59	37.8
Both hard and soft	78	50.0
No response	3	1.9
Additional courses		
Yes	65	41.7
No	87	55.8
No response	4	2.6

A total of 153 students from the three institutions participated in the survey. They are mainly from Civil (18%), Electrical (11%), Mechanical (55%) and ICT (9.5%). Approximately 22% are in their third year, 24% in their fourth year, and 34% in their final year.

Availability of Computer tools and mode of lectures

About half (50.3%) of the students who participated have a laptop, while all the participants reported having a smartphone. Almost 48% of the participants prefer a mixed-mode approach, 34% prefer physical

in-person lectures, while 18% prefer the online mode. About 10.5% of students prefer hard copies, 36.6% prefer soft copies, while 51% of students prefer both hard and soft copies, with only 10% wanting hard copies only. A crosstab analysis reveals a significant difference between students with laptops, who prefer a mixed mode of both online and physical lectures, and those without laptops, who prefer physical classrooms. $\chi^2(4, N=153)=11.63, p=0.02$.

Concerning courses received online, approximately 38% have only a course taught

online, and another 24% reported taking two courses, while 8% reported taking three courses within the last academic year. This is despite more than 60% taking more than 14 courses within the previous academic session. More than 60% of the students are satisfied with receiving lectures in person, compared to about 52% who prefer the online mode. In comparison, 16% and 26% are less enthusiastic about in-person and online lectures, respectively. Figure 1 shows students' satisfaction level with physical and online lectures ($r = 0.59, p \leq 0.001$).

Figure 7 Students' Satisfaction level with online and Physical lectures

Platform

The most commonly reported online learning platforms are Google Classroom (71.3%), Zoom (24.7%), YouTube (10%), and Microsoft Teams (6.7%). Most participants (57.2%) have not taken courses not associated with their school courses on

online platforms like Coursera, YouTube, edX, etc.

Broadband availability

Figure 2 shows that 55% of the participants use personal subscriptions on mobile providers for internet access compared to less than 40% who use school wifi. Only 6% visit the school ICT centre for internet access.

Figure 8 Sources of Internet Usage

Use of AI for learning

The most common Artificial intelligence tools used by students are products of OpenAI’s ChatGPT-3.5 (39.3%) and ChatGPT-4.0 (25.5%). Others are playground (20.7%), Google Bard (23.4%),

and stepwise Math (7.6%). Figure 3 shows that AI tools are primarily used for assignments (58.7%) and to gain a better understanding of topics and concepts (53.3%). While 53.3% use it for more understanding, and less than 20% use it for language and grammar checking.

Figure 9 What AI Tools are used for

Students' Perception of AI Use

About 39% of the students perceived that lecturers have a positive reaction to the use of AI, while about 27% show a negative outlook on its use. However, about 34% of the lecturers are perceived to be indifferent. More than 72% of the students believe that using AI enhance the learning of Engineering, and about 17% are indifferent. Only about 11% of the participants perceive that the use of AI won't improve learning. However, about 40% of the students agree that AI makes students lazy, while about 24% disagree that AI causes laziness. Despite the earlier notion, more than 60% still believe that the use of AI is more advantageous in Engineering, with less than 10% thinking otherwise. Correlational analysis reveals a significant correlation between students' opinions about AI enhancing learning and the perception that AI has more advantages than disadvantages ($r = 0.447, p < 0.0001$). It was also reported that there is a significant difference in students' preferences for a particular mode of teaching and their perception of AI as advantageous or not ($F(2,147) = 3.147, p = 0.045$). However,

there was no difference in the response regarding AI advantages between those with a laptop and those without a laptop, $t(0.146) = 1.095, p = 0.276$. However, there was no correlation between AI-enhancing learning and making students lazy ($r = 0.155, p = 0.06$), nor between AI being more advantageous and making students lazy ($r = 0.078, p = 0.345$).

It also shows a significant correlation between teachers' reactions to AI use by students and their opinions about AI enhancing learning and being more advantageous ($r = 0.25, p = 0.002$). However, the ICC reveals good reliability (agreement) with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.562, indicating that the AI is not considered to make students lazy.

Students have a more positive outlook on the use of AI in engineering education. This also aligns with the lecturers' reaction, as they encourage its use as a means of supporting teaching. Most lecturers are still reluctant to adopt the online mode of teaching, as indicated by the students' responses. Most of the lectures are conducted on a platform that has a free version.

Discussion

The availability of learning facilities can influence students' interest in e-learning, especially in engineering education. Engineering students reported that online learning is more expensive and that teaching practical or laboratory instructions online is complicated. (Abdulkareem et al., 2022). The requirement for software and programmes to support practical activities creates a serious demand for online learning. (Abdulkareem et al., 2022). The availability of the facilities influenced the students' willingness to use the e-learning system. (Balogun et al., 2023). Scarcity of computers, electricity, and the cost of power are major barriers to students' learning and lecturers' job satisfaction. As shown in this study, a significant number of students still prefer face-to-face learning, and students with laptops tend to prefer a mixed mode of learning compared to those without laptops. Although most students have smartphones, laptops are generally considered better for school learning than mobile phones. Laptops provide a wider screen and also a better interface for multiple viewing and multitasking. Although laptops are available at the ICT centres of all participating schools, fewer than 10% of the students visit these centres. The students' preference for smartphones for learning has been reported both locally and internationally (Gamage & Perera, 2021; Taiwo et al., 2022). Students' reliance on broadband instead of wifi is a limitation, as students with available wifi and laptop use are reported to achieve better remote learning outcomes than those who rely on mobile broadband. (Chisadza et al., 2021).

E-learning is not yet a popular mode of teaching engineering in the Northwest region of the country. Only about 62% of the

students reported taking only one or two courses online. This approach by the lecturers is similar to what is available in other regions of the country, as lecturers are familiar with students' attitudes and facility limitations (Kuliya & Usman, 2021). Lecturers are also aware that, although virtual or online laboratories improve engineering learning, students who have only smartphones may not benefit fully due to the limited screen size and processing power of the phones, which may not be sufficient to run most laptop-friendly software (Li & Liang, 2024). Most of the students do not learn outside the classroom. This may be because of the lower reliability of the school's Wi-Fi. It may also contribute to the students' preference for physical classrooms, as online or e-learning places additional demand for internet connectivity on them. The study also shows that most students use broadband rather than free institutional wifi. Since many stayed off-campus, their reliance on broadband is a challenge. This is similar to what is obtainable in the entire sub-Saharan African (Chisadza et al., 2021).

The nonavailability of reliable internet facilities and students' lack of laptops and personal facilities affect the students' desire for online study. A similar Nigerian study has earlier identified that digital gaps in device ownership, internet, and electricity availability significantly deter students' participation in online study (Olanrewaju et al., 2021). The findings in the study are related to what was observed in other sub-Saharan countries (Adzifome & Agyei, 2023; Ndibalema, 2025; Nkansah & Oldac, 2024).

AI Usage

The popularity of ChatGPT among the students is similar to what is obtainable in other institutions locally and internationally. (Ravšelj et al., 2025; Stöhr et al., 2024; Ya'u

& Mohammed, 2025). Students' usage of such tools mainly for assignments, understanding of topics is also well documented, as is the limited usage for Grammatical checking (Ahmed et al., 2024; Baek et al., 2024). The findings reveal the limited use of AI for learning purposes, as Engineering students are expected to benefit more from it than what was reported. The students have not taken advantage of the increase in the online Engineering programme, as only a few take Engineering-related courses online.

Limitations of the Study

The study has some limitations as a cross-sectional study. The observations do not depict causality, which implies that the observations are limited to associations. Self-reported opinions can also be biased, as the respondents might give socially desirable answers. However, with the improvement in infrastructure and purchasing power of students, which may happen soon with the recently introduced student loan facilities, the opinions and observations in the study may change over time. Also, the sample size is limited, especially as it does not capture the lower-level undergraduates. Also, the online survey may have prevented those without smartphones and internet access from participating.

Conclusion

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic led to the online development of engineering programs. Nigerian students, especially engineering students in the Northwestern part of the country, have not maximised the opportunities that the event has presented for learning Engineering programmes. The students are affected by the availability of adequate facilities that would enhance their

interest in online studies. The lack of such facilities affected the perception of the benefit that accrues from online engineering education, which could complement the limited teaching resources that are available in the institutions. Lecturers and instructors could also increase their online presence to encourage students' utilisation of online facilities.

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